

Analysis of Classroom Interaction Using Flander Interaction Analysis Categories System at Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State

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Abstract

This paper examined Classroom Interaction using Flanders' Interaction Analysis Categories System at Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State. The purpose was to find out the percentage of the teachers' and students' talking time during classroom interaction and teacher-students characteristics during classroom interaction in Business Studies class at the College Demonstration Secondary School. The research adopted a descriptive qualitative research design. The study comprised of four teachers and 32 students of boys and girls which were purposively sampled. The observational and video recording techniques were deployed as instruments for data collection. The result found that teacher talk ratio was high, at 83.43%. Indirect teacher talk ratio was 53.37%. Moreover, direct teacher talk ratio was 31.06% while students talk ratio was 12.71% and silence or pause or confusion rate was 3.86%. The results further revealed that indirect talk was dominant than direct talk in the classroom conversation which indicated that most of the teaching-learning time was devoted to questions, lecturing and praises. The result of this research enhanced the knowledge of the teachers and Business Studies learners in the classroom. The implication was that both the teachers and students should have the willingness to participate in the classroom interaction for meaningful learning to take place. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Flanders Interaction Analysis Categories System should be implemented during teachers education program to be reinforced at all levels in all the classes for enhanced performance.

Keywords: *Classroom Interaction, Flanders Interaction Analysis Categories System, Teacher's talk, Student's talk.*

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Introduction

The world we are living as humans is a dynamic and complex system having inter-relationship of different people and demographics. The older has the responsibility of indoctrinating the young ones in order to transmit societal values, norms, culture, knowledge and develop skills for functional life. These, however, cannot be possible without meaningful interaction. This in addition is done in the process of teaching and learning. The teacher and the learners must interact so as to pass on knowledge, share ideas and teach skills with appropriate feedback.

Passivity in the classroom is partly due to the methods some teachers use in teaching. When less responsibility for learning is given to learners, they will be passive. However, in a purposeful classroom interaction where students are adequately engaged, interaction is warm and is seen as exchange of ideas. Teachers should not take responsibility for student's learning but create opportunity for it (Ayish, 2019). Teachers are to motivate learners to respond, react and participate during the learning session. It is when teacher incites students to participate that learning becomes meaningful and enduring. Feedback involves students sharing their ideas, expressing their fears and doubts in a meaningful way.

Classroom interaction generally and particularly in Business Studies teaching and learning environment is seen as a two-way process. It is a give and take, cause- and-effect and reciprocal process. It is also dynamic and prevails in social setting of the classroom. In today's world, classroom is not only fixed and physical but virtual and whichever is the case, the elements and characteristics of reciprocity holds true. Through classroom interaction teachers can dutifully encourage his students to speak, react, because, it is only in this way that they can understand what the teacher teaches and gives their responders.

The type of teacher talk would go a long way in either stimulating the students' participation, engagement and achievement. Conventional and traditional teaching methods indulge learners in passivity. However, if the teacher adopts a cooperative and democratic system of communication, otherwise referred to as innovative teaching strategies, it would be easy for students to be involved and feel a sense of belonging. Constructivist teaching methodologies are highly sort after today because they give more responsibilities to learners for their learning. If on the other hand a teacher is autocratic and assume a sage or the stage, the student would only be passive listeners and loss out in meaningful learning and performance. Indirect teacher talk represents the former while direct teach talk makes students only onlookers.

Flanders interaction analysis categories system is deemed very appropriate in analyzing business studies classroom interaction. This is typically true since the system measures both the teacher and students talk during learning and teaching process. The model measure what the teacher and students do during their classroom interaction. Its analysis centres on verbal discourse and non-verbal gestures. The system is such a holistic as in addition to teachers and students talk time also captures doubts, or confusion or time of silence during the interaction (Amatari, 2015).

Previous studies reveal teachers talk were dominant during classroom interaction. Some of these studies such as Ulan (2017), Nurmasitah, (2010) Tuan and Nhu (2010) indicated that classroom interaction was more of teacher-centredness. The teacher took more talk time than the students. Based on these studies the researcher's intent in this research was simply find out how students and teacher participate to talk during classroom teaching and learning process. Through this research the researcher would be disposed to ascertain the teachers and students talking time and characteristics in a more precise fashion.

Statement of Problem

More often than not, what an average person, be it student, teacher, administrator and other stakeholders in the education enterprise could decipher whenever there is a class session for teaching and learning is that interaction takes place between a teacher and his students. Simply, to them, classroom interact is characterized by giving and receiving. Many may not know how much verbal talk ratio ensured between both players in the classroom setting nor the implication of the disparity that may result from the interaction. Will analysis of classroom interaction however not reveal the behind-the-scene activities which are highly crucial as how much talk time (ratio) individual players take during classroom verbal interaction? If it is revealed that a teacher talks far more than the students, the implication is a teacher-centred class and vice versa. Additionally will this deeper knowledge of what takes place during teaching and learning endeavor inform the stakeholders why students achievements level is either desirable or below expectation?

Research Objectives

The objectives of the research are to determine;

1. The total teacher's talk ratio
2. To find out ratio of teacher's direct talk
3. To find teacher's indirect talk ratio
4. To find out students' talk ratio
5. To find out ratio of silence or confusion

Research Questions

1. What is the teacher talk ratio?
2. What is the ratio of teacher's direct talk?
3. What is the teacher's indirect talk ratio?
4. What ratio represents students' talk?
5. What is the ratio of silence or confusion?

Literature Review

Meaning of Classroom Interaction

Merriam Webster dictionary defines interaction as the action or influence of people, groups, or things on one another. Interaction according to the Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary (2008) is when there are two or more persons or things communicate with or react to each other. To these definitions the point of interaction

in general is a reciprocal relationship among individuals that occur in the shared community. Flanders in Arockiasamy (2019) defines, teaching as an interactive proceeding. To him interaction means participation of teacher and students in the process of teaching and learning. In this process, teacher influences the students; students also interact with the teacher in a reciprocal way.

Interaction no doubt takes place among the students themselves also. It means, in the procedure of teaching, everybody interacts with every other person involved in the process. Teacher influences students through lecture, questionings, criticizing, exercising authority giving directions etc. Students on the other hand respond and react to the teacher's lecture and questions, as the situation demands. It is interaction between teachers and students that brings about learning in the classroom. In the assertion of Niki (2011) classroom communication in the school environment is a key element in the teaching and learning process. A crucial component of effective classroom teaching is the quality and quantity of teacher-student interaction. Niki (2011) added that the word 'interaction' means an action-reaction or a shared or reciprocal effect that may be between individuals, e.g. pupil – pupil; teacher-pupil in classroom environment, or between materials and individuals or groups.

The term classroom interaction refers to the interaction between the teacher and learners, and amongst the learners, in the classroom (Tsui, 2010). Tsui (2010) averred that earlier studies of classroom interaction focused on the language used by the teacher and learners, the interaction generated, and their effect on learning. More recent studies have begun to investigate the underlying factors which shape interaction in the classroom – e.g. teacher and learner beliefs, social and cultural background of the teacher and learners, and the psychological aspects of the key players in the classroom which provide further insights into the complexities of classroom interaction. This is one of the reasons more research should be carried out into classroom interactions

According to Allwright in Tsui (2010), classroom interaction research began in the 1960s with the aim of evaluating the effectiveness of different methods used in teaching in the hope that the findings would show the 'best' method and its characteristics. The methodology adopted then was strongly influenced by first language classroom teaching research which was motivated by the need to assess objectively the teaching performance of student-teachers during practical teaching. Various classroom observation instruments have been proposed to capture the language used by the teacher and the interaction generated. These interaction analysis studies revealed that classroom processes are extremely complex and that a prescriptive approach to ascertain the 'best' method would be fundamentally flawed if the descriptive techniques are inadequate. Research efforts therefore turned to coping with problems of description and the focus of classroom interaction studies shifted from prescriptive to descriptive and from evaluative to awareness-raising and advocacy.

Flanders Interaction Analysis Category System

According to Zhao (2021), Ned A. Flanders developed a system of interaction analysis to study what happens in a classroom when a teacher teaches. It is known as Flanders Interaction Analysis Categories System. Flanders and others developed this system at the University of Minnesota, U.S.A. between 1955 and 1960. Flanders cited in Kapoe (2021) classified total verbal behavior in the classroom into 10 categories and their meanings. The classroom verbal behavior broadly comprises teacher talk, student talk

and silence, pause or confusion. Teacher talk is subdivided into two; Indirect (category 1-4) and direct teacher talk (category 5-7); student talk (category 8-9) while pause or confusion or silence (category 10).

Zhao 2021 and Kapoe (2021) give the meaning of the various categories are explained them as follows:

1. Teacher Talk (7 Categories)

a.) Indirect Talk: In this method of analysis, the first four categories represent the teacher's indirect influence in the classroom.

Category 1: Accepts Feelings- In this category, teacher accommodates the feelings of the students. His perception here is that the students should not be reprimanded for exhibiting his feelings which may be negative or positive.

Category 2: Praise or Encouragement- It is a fact that the use of appropriate reinforcement by every teacher should be encouraged in the classroom. Here the Teacher praises or encourages student action or behavior. This is done when a student gives answer to the question asked by the teacher, the teacher gives positive reward by saying words like 'good' 'better', 'correct', 'excellent', my Prof, etc.

Category 3: Accepts or Uses ideas of students

This similar to the first category. However, in this category, only the pupil's ideas are accepted only and not his feelings. An instance is when a student offers some suggestions, the teacher may respond by repeating it precisely either in his own words or style he deemed fit. The teacher can simply affirm by say, 'I understand what your means, your idea is in line etc. Or the teacher builds on the idea, refines clarifies, builds the ideas or suggestions given by a student in question.

Category 4: Asking Questions

The teacher with the content knowledge of the topic asks students questions based on content and procedures and expect response from the students. A question that was left unanswered does not belong to this category.

b.) Direct Talk:

Category 5: Lecture/Lecturing

Here, the teacher gives his opinion about the procedure or content of the topic being taught. He cites authority, gives personal ideas and explanation other than that of the students.

Category 6: Giving Directions

The teacher gives directions, commands or orders or initiation with which a pupil/student is expected to comply with. Open your exercise books, repeat after me, look at the chalkboard, etc. are worthy examples here.

Category 7: or Justifying Authority or Criticizing

When the teacher cautions the students not to disrupt the class with irrelevant questions, this conduct is allowed in this category. Teacher's 'how', 'what' and 'why' also takes into account here.

2. Pupil Talk (2 Categories)

Category 8: Pupil Talk Response

It includes the students talk in response to teacher's talk. Teacher asks question, student gives answer to the question.

Category 9: Pupil Talk Initiation

Talk by students that they initiate. Expressing own ideas; initiating a new topic; freedom to develop opinions and a line of thought like asking thoughtful questions; going beyond the existing structure.

Category 10: Silence or Pause or Confusion

This is moments of pauses, momentary silence and period of confusion occasioned by break in communication. The observer among other things cannot understand what is being said. A time could come when the teacher instructs students

to open their text book, say to page 34. The pause and silence that ensued while they look for that page represents this category.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive qualitative design approach. It consisted of a population of four Business Studies teachers and thirty two students of mixed gender; Boys twenty two and girls seven of an intact class. The sample size of 32 was purposively sampled because of certain criteria which among others are teachers must have above five years teaching experience and teachers must be certified by Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN). The observational and video recording technique was deployed for the collection of data for the study. Equipped with the observation tally sheet and video recording gargets, the researcher sits in the classroom in the best position to listen and see the teachers and students. The class sessions were video recorded for the purpose of comparing the result with the researcher's coding. Thus the time involves in coding one tally for every 3 seconds, is 20 tallies in one minute, 100 tallies in 5 minutes and 1200 tallies in one hour. In this process only the serial numbers of the categories are recorded. The serial number of that category is recorded on the data sheet by the observer. When the observation is over, the observer shifts to some other room and prepares the details on the basis of those serial numbers of the categories. In this observation process, the writing of serial numbers of the categories is known as encoding. Writing details of behavior on the basis of these categories is known as decoding.

Data collected were analysed using percentage.

Results and Discussion

As mentioned in the research methodology, to get the data, the researcher conducted observation using observation tally sheet and recording. In addition, to know the percentage of talk time during the classroom interaction, the researcher used Flanders formula. Then, to know the characteristics of the students and the lecturer, the researcher used Flanders Interaction Matrix. Finally, after all of the data collected, the researcher analyzed each data. Firstly. The result of classroom observation and

recording described the reality of classroom interaction between the lecturer and the students. Below are the percentages of talk time during the classroom interaction.

Table 1. The percentage of talk time

Number	Classroom Interaction	
1	Teacher Talk Ratio	83.43%
2	Indirect Teacher talk Ratio	52.37%
3	Direct Teacher Talk Ratio	31.06%
4	Student's Talk Ratio	12.71%
5	Silence or Confusion Ratio	3.86%

1. Teacher Talk Ratio

Based on the data of the talk time during the conversation class, it was found that the teacher talk ratio is 83.43%. In fact, the role of teachers in the classroom interaction had a great impact on the result of the findings. In this case, when students have low motivation to build a communication in the classroom during the class, then the teacher tend to hold the class in order to decrease the rigid situation in the classroom. The case showed the teacher has the main role in controlling the class (Rindu and Ariyanti, 2017). In addition, the teacher made a big effort to create the atmosphere in the classroom to stimulate student's motivation to interact with other students and with the teacher. Moreover, the teacher spent much talk time during the classroom interaction to organize all these activities.

2. Indirect Teacher Talk Ratio

The talk time during the conversation class found that the indirect teacher talk ratio was 52.37%. The result showed that the teacher indirectly showed her response to the students' feelings and accepting students' feelings, accepting students' ideas by clarifying and developing their ideas mostly. In addition, the lecturer indirectly praises her students and encourages them to interact with other students in the classroom. Moreover, in order to know students' knowledge or concept about the lesson, the teacher indirectly asked questions mostly during the classroom interaction (Matra, 2014). The teacher supported students' participation during the classroom interaction.

3. Direct Teacher Talk Ratio

Based on the data of the talk time during the conversation class, it was found that the direct teacher talk ratio is 31.06%. The result showed that the teacher diminished her teaching, giving direction and criticizing the students. Seemingly, the lecturer gave chance to the students to comprehend the content or concept of the lesson themselves without teaching or giving direction and commands. In this case, the teacher builds students' motivation to learn independently (Filgona, 2020).

4. Students' Talk Ratio/Percentage of Students Talk

It was found that the students talk ratio is 12.71%. The result showed that students' participation in the conversation class was low. In this class, there were three or four students who speak actively and responded to the lecturer's question. Most of them, doing usual activity and await directions, commands or instruction from the teacher. Therefore, it seemed the lecture had a major control in the class because most of the students had low motivation to speak and interact with other students. The teacher

tried to encourage and motivate them by giving praise, storytelling or jokes to stimulate their willingness to speak bravely (Anggreni, Hastini and Emiwani, 2019).

5. Silence or Confusion Ratio

Based on the data of the talk time during the conversation class, it was found that the silence or confusion rate was 3.86%. The result showed that silence or confusion in the conversation class was very low. It means that there was a little confusion in communication during the class in a short period (Onwioduokit and Chika, 2012). Moreover, the activity in the conversation class was recorded well so that it diminished the confusion of communication.

Conclusions

Based on the data analysis and the result of the study, it can be concluded that teacher talk ratio dominated the classroom interaction. Most of the class conversation was handled and controlled by the teacher. This rightly inferred that the classroom interaction was merely teacher-centred with less engagement, participation by the students. Passivity of students characterized the class atmosphere suggesting the adoption of traditional rather than innovative teaching strategies and methodologies. Teacher indirect talk was higher followed by his direct. Students talk ratio showed that students' participation in the conversation class was low. In this class, there were three or four students who speak actively and respond to the lecturer's questions. They assumed this position because they were introverts. Both students talk and Silence or confusion rates showed that silence and confusion were very low. It means that there were less involvement by the learners and little confusion in communication during the class in a short period. Indirect and direct ratio showed that direct talk was dominant than direct talk in the conversation class. The scenario in this class reflected that most of the teaching-learning time was devoted to questions, lecturing and praises.

For this reason, it is better to mix the teaching-learning time by varied materials, strategies, styles, methods and approaches. In addition, it is better if the teacher gives more reinforcements to the students. Engaging the students through activities could increase the frequency of productive behaviors and decrease the frequency of disruptive behaviors.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the researcher offers the following recommendations:

1. Trainee teachers should be taught the Flanders Model as a mandatory topic in order for them to be abreast with the nitty-gritty of what ensue in the classroom.
2. Various strategies that enhance students' engagement during classroom interaction should be employed by teachers to adequately balance the teacher student talk ratio during teaching learning process.
3. ICT should be used by both teacher and student as a way of pre-informing student with topic and material content to be taught as a way of enhancing student preparation for meaningful participation in the upcoming lesson.

4. Teachers and students should be aware of the paradigm shift in their roles in teaching learning process; teacher should be more as a facilitator and students assuming more responsibility for their learning in order to engender sustainable learning.

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